

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

TPS2 - a new variety for Kanyakumari

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TPS2, a derivative of IR26/CO 40 developed at the Thiruppathisaram Rice Research Station, has been released. The semidwarf (90-95 cm) with 125 d

duration is suitable for second season (Sep-Oct) sowing. In testing at the research station and in adaptive research trials over the entire Kanyakumari district, it had 16.6-31.4% increases in grain yield and 27.6-48.8% increases in straw yield over IR20 (see table).

TPS2 is moderately resistant to brown planthopper, leafhopper, and white tip nematode. It is nonlodging and nonshattering. Grain is bold, with a 1,000-grain weight of 23.5 g. □

Characteristics of TPS2 in Kanyakumari, India, 1979-86.

Variety	Grain yield		Straw yield		Duration (d)
	t/ha	% increase	t/ha	% increase	
	<i>Station trials^a</i>				
TPS2	4.6	31.4	6.4	48.8	125
IR20	3.5	—	4.3	—	125
	<i>Adaptive research trials, 1982-83</i>				
TPS2	4.1	20.1	10.8	31.7	125
IR20	3.4	—	8.2	—	125
	<i>Adaptive research trials, 1983-84</i>				
TPS2	4.2	16.6	7.4	27.6	123
IR20	3.6	—	5.8	—	123

^aMean of 1979-86.

Dominant dwarf mutants in rice induced with fractionated dose of gamma rays

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Presoaked seeds (24 h in distilled water) of TKM6 were exposed to gamma rays

of 35 kR in split or fractionated treatments with 4-h intervals between each exposure. The treatments were 0, 35 kR in a single dose, 30 + 5 kR, 25 + 10 kR, 20 + 15 kR, 15 + 20 kR, 10 + 25 kR, and 5 + 30 kR. In the first generation (M₁), plants survived from only 3 treatments: 5 + 30 kR (3 plants), 30 + 5 kR (5 plants), and 20 + 15 kR

Table 1. Performance of dominant dwarf mutants of TKM6 in the M₁. Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Yield/plant (g)
5 + 30 kR	84	11	22.9	6.2
30 + 5 kR	84	15	21.5	20.9
20 + 15 kR	85	17	20.9	19.6
Control	150	12	23.3	9.2